

Sevinc Tangudur

Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences
department of Architecture and Art Institute

Senior researcher in the “History and theory of architecture”

Full member of the International Academy of Architecture
of Eastern Countries (IAAEC),

Professor International Academy of Architecture (IAAM), Moscow Branch

IAAM EURASIA Doctor of Philosophy in Architecture,

Associate Professor,

UDC 72.03**THE ROLE OF GREAT LEADER HEYDAR ALIYEV IN THE
DEVELOPMENT OF ARCHITECTURE OF AZERBAIJAN**

Abstract: In many cases, the formation of the country and the state is connected with the name of geniuses raised by the people. The formation of modern Azerbaijan, the establishment and development of an independent republic coincided with the years 1969-1982 and 1993-2003, when the great leader Heydar Aliyev led the state. At a time when economic development is observed in our country, the role of Heydar Aliyev in the rapid rise in the field of architecture and construction is irreplaceable.

Heydar Aliyev, an art-loving personality who wanted to become an architect as his first dream, later, he became a political architect as the head of Azerbaijan and was able to create a very valuable legacy. From time to time, this heritage will be the focus of scientific-practical research, professional views, and will be studied.

Keywords: Heydar Aliyev, Great leader, National leader

The arrival of the national leader to Azerbaijan in 1969 was primarily aimed at the development of industry and agriculture, which was possible due to the construction of new modern industrial enterprises, socio-cultural, service and infrastructure facilities in the country. Realization of these large-scale programs was possible due to the parallel development of the current situation in the construction field. The reforms initiated by Heydar Aliyev made it possible to achieve serious progress in such directions as the development of the construction materials industry, the strengthening of the material and technical base of the field, and the training of new personnel. And this has led to the increase of the main indicators of construction several times compared to previous years, to the timely and high-quality commissioning of important objects under construction. Among them, one can cite the Kura

aqueduct, "Neftchilar" and "Nizami" metro stations, the processing complex of the New Baku Oil Refinery, the Baku Household Air Conditioners plant, the huge Deep Oil Plant in the Garadag region, and many others. [1].

It should be noted that Baku, the capital of Azerbaijan, changed its face during the time of the great leader, in 1969-1982, as a result of development and improvement. New buildings, cultural facilities were put into use, and the construction of residential houses was carried out on a large scale. The multi-apartment buildings built during these years made it possible to provide one out of every three residents of Azerbaijan with a new apartment in that period. The magnificent "Gulüstan" palace, which has a special place in the architecture of the city, has hosted important events for many years, and is intended for mass events of the republic, was built in 1979-1980 on the initiative of Heydar Aliyev. In 1994, on September 20, the agreement of the century was signed here by the great leader. (photo.1)

Figure 1. Gulistan Palace, 1980

Figure 2. View of Gulistan Palace on June 24, 2021 after repair and reconstruction

Figure 3. H. Aliyev - Gulustan Palace, 1982 "For "Bolshoi Theater" artists organized feast.

Figure 4. H. Aliyev - Gulustan Palace, 1982 Meeting with heads of foreign diplomatic missions.

For the second time during his rule, during the years 1993-2003, the comprehensive measures implemented by Heydar Aliyev in the direction of construction, improvement and solving socio-ecological problems in Azerbaijan were reflected in the improvement of the social conditions of the population as a result. Socially, solving environmental problems in residential areas is interconnected with the living conditions of the population. Appreciating the importance of urban planning in improving the household culture of the population, the great leader from the first days of his leadership in Azerbaijan paid serious attention to urban planning in large industrial cities such as Baku, Sumgayit and Ganja. Heydar Aliyev, talking about urban planning issues, specially noted that a lot of work has been done in this field in Baku.

He emphasized that the planning of urban development on scientific basis and the continuation of construction works are important issues for the capital. In 1996, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Heydar Aliyev, during his speech at the opening ceremony of the new building of the International Bank in Baku, expressed his immense love for the motherland, his attitude to his work, and his enthusiasm for construction and creativity:

"I consider every stone, every street, every building of the city to be native to me. If everyone loves his nation, city, homeland and Baku, our capital, he should live with such feelings." [3]

In 1998, the national leader, together with other state officials, participated in the ceremonial opening of the administrative building of the Central Bank, which is currently operating after the International Bank. (foto 5)

Figure 5. H. Aliyev - opening of the administrative building of the Central Bank, 1998

It should not be forgotten that the great leader is not only the founder of the modern Azerbaijan state, but also the architect of modern settlements. Heydar Aliyev was personally interested in every new building that was important in terms of urban planning in Baku, visited it during its construction, and organized the solution of the problems that arose during its construction by giving relevant tasks to the relevant persons. One of such buildings was the

first 18-story residential building built in 1997-1999 next to the old Absheron hotel, and the great leader visited the construction site many times and was interested in the progress of its construction. (photo 6.)

Figure 6. The residential building visited by H. Aliyev during its construction, 1997-1999

The new era that started in the cultural life of our people in the 20th century is an era associated with the name of the great leader Heydar Aliyev. The great leader said that "the nation is known and recognized for its many characteristics and stands out among the nations of the world. The highest and greatest of these features is culture." That is why the great leader always focused on the development of the people's culture during all the periods he was in power. [2] Many cinemas, theater buildings, and museums were built during the reign of the great leader, who paid special attention to strengthening the material and technical base of culture. Closed theaters, libraries, museums began to operate again, many performance institutions, including the Philharmonic, were put into use after renovation. The inclusion of Icherisheher, which reflects the ancient urban planning traditions of Azerbaijan, together with the Shirvanshahs Palace Complex, into the list of UNESCO's material heritage was a great historical event.

Heydar Aliyev paid attention to the preservation of national architectural and urban planning rules during the construction works. He recommended giving wide space to national architectural forms in newly built buildings, effectively using national patterns in the interiors and exteriors of buildings, which is one of the factors that show the great leader's deep love for our national culture. The genius leader prefers to stay devoted to the Eastern style and our national culture in housing construction, and he reminded everyone about it. One of the issues he constantly emphasized was related to the wide use of elements of Azerbaijani architecture that give buildings an Eastern color in their work. He stated that the constructed ensembles and individual buildings are the future of Baku, and they should please our future generations. It was as a result of his great efforts that huge construction works based on

historical architectural traditions were carried out in all regions of Azerbaijan.

During the years of regaining its independence, the modern Republic of Azerbaijan has gone through a complicated and at the same time honorable path. The large-scale reforms carried out under the leadership of our great leader Heydar Aliyev and President Ilham Aliyev, who is a worthy follower of his ideas, served to improve the socio-economic situation in our country and further increase the material welfare of the population. As a result of the far-sighted policy, which was founded by the National leader and is successfully implemented today, many social issues have been resolved, important steps have been taken to strengthen the social protection of the population and further improve living conditions.

Literature:

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S. Tangudur

Ulu öndər Heydər Əliyevin Azərbaycanın memarlığının inkişafında rolu

Açar sözlər: Heydər Əliyev, Ulu öndər, Ümummilli lider.

Ölkənin, dövlətin formalaşması bir çox hallarda xalqın yetişirdiyi dahi şəxsiyyətlərin adı ilə bağlı olur. Müasir Azərbaycanın formalaşması, müstəqil respublikanın qurulması və inkişafına təkan verilməsi Ulu öndər Heydər Əliyevin dövlətə rəhbərlik etdiyi 1969-1982 və 1993-2003-cü illərə təsadüf edir. Bu dövrlərdə ölkəmizdə iqtisadi baxımdan inkişaf müşahidə olunduğu bir dövrdə memarlıq və tikinti sahəsində sürətli artımında Heydər Əliyevin rolu əvəzolunmazdır.

İlk arzusu memar olmaq istəyən incəsənət meyilli şəxsiyyət Heydər Əliyev, sonralar Azərbaycanın rəhbəri kimi siyasət memarına çevrilərək çox dəyərli irs yarada bilmişdir. Bu irs zaman-zaman elmi-praktik araşdırmaların, peşəkar baxışların diqqət mərkəzində olacaq, tədqiq ediləcəkdir.

С. Тангудур

Роль великого лидера Гейдара Алиева в развитии архитектуры Азербайджана

Ключевые слова: Гейдар Алиев, Великий лидер, национальный лидер.

Становление государства, часто бывает связано с именами выдающихся личностей. Формирование и развитие современной Республики Азербайджан приходится на период руководство страной Великого лидера Гейдара Алиева в 1969-1982 и в 1993-2003 гг. В этот период, в стране наблюдалось бурное экономическое развитие в области архитектуры и строительства, и, роль Гейдара Алиева в этом процессе - незаменима.

Личность Гейдара Алиева, первым желанием которого было стать архитектором, позднее состоялся как лидер и архитектор современного Азербайджана. Безусловно это наследие будет находиться в центре внимания научно-практических исследований, профессиональных взглядов и будет изучаться.